

Newspaper Discourse: Features of Speech Influence in Uzbek and American Newspapers

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Annotation:

Language is identified and analyzed as a method that forms linguistic and cultural space in mass media, as well as influencing thinking system of a person, on the style of world perception, on the type of culture of today. Data obtained as part of the presented scientific research based on the study numerous domestic and foreign authoritative sources and refereed periodicals devoted to the problems of the impact of language on a person as a direct participant in mass media, contribute to further development for the language itself. The scientific research have theoretical significance, which lies in the systematic study of linguistic phenomena in the linguistic and cultural sphere and the possibility of cognition using language as a way to influence the psycho-emotional perception of information in mass media.

Keywords: mass communication, mass media, language, culture, development and influence of language, mediators, interpersonality, euphemization and dysphemization.

Language and culture are interrelated concepts that reflect only the reality of the surrounding the world, an individual person, but also the public self-awareness of people, their mentality, national characteristics, traditional values, moral principles and their worldview. A person perceives the world through what he says, and people speaking different languages perceive the surrounding reality differently, since each of us has our own picture of the world in our minds, laid down by the culture and experience of previous generations. Being in communication, a person enriches the language, pushing the boundaries such a concept as mass communication. At the same time, great importance is attached to the semantic load of the word as a unit of the linguocultural aspect. Given the reality of the current time, we can observe a transformation in the methods of transmitting information to the media. And from this point of view, language is of interest as a method that shapes linguistic and cultural space. M.V. Shkondin points out, “if science creates a scientific

picture of the world, art creates an artistic picture, then journalism as a type of creativity produces, creates such an information product as a holistic picture of current reality and no one, apart from her, he does not perform this important work for society” [1, 7-9 p]. Spiritual products created by journalists (in the genres of reporting, interviews, commentary, correspondence, etc.) represent the result of a systematic and continuous practical-spiritual exploration of the world.

The active nature of journalists, acting as mediators, their powerful energetic properties explain the fact that both the word, the symbol, and the myth may have both creative and enormous destructive power. The most important condition for the existence of mediators is that people treat them only as intermediaries, based on free, consciously responsible activity in their use. When contacting the media, the reader also becomes a communicator, transmitting information, and a communicator, participating in the communication process. The problem of the influence of language on a person, his way of thinking and his behavior today is directly related to the media. By informing a person about the state of the world and filling his leisure time, the media influence the entire structure of his thinking, the style of worldview, and the type of culture of today.

Newspaper discourse is defined as a communicative phenomenon, an environment in which a newspaper text “ripes” and is created. The discourse does not include only the text itself, but also various extralinguistic components (knowledge of world, opinions, values), which play an important role in understanding and perception of information. The elements of discourse are the events being presented, the participants of these events, performative information and circumstances accompanying the events, background, assessment of the participants of the event, etc. Newspaper discourse is a dynamic cognitive-communicative phenomenon, the process and result of speech communication in print media; newspaper text is a product of discursive activity in the conditions of mass communication, facilitating the exchange of socially significant, relevant information. A special type of speech communication – mass information – unites various genre forms within the framework of newspaper discourse. Dynamic situation genre formation in modern newspaper discourse indicates a certain flexibility of the newspaper genre system, including core varieties of journalistic texts (actually informational, information-analytical and analytical) and peripheral (artistic-publicistic).

This specificity of print media forces the reader to have a certain image of the publication that he wants to buy or subscribe to its thematic, ideological, political, and directed to his style. It is necessary here note that the reader’s interest can be directed both to the publication as a whole, as to the product of a certain way of reflecting reality, expressed in the form of a set of messages that meet his specific requests, as well as materials written by individual journalists working in the publication. This corresponds to the idea expressed by I.V. Silantiev, about the two poles of journalistic discourse in domestic journalism: “Accordingly, two poles can be distinguished in journalistic discourse - in the terminology of V.I. Karasik is a pole of interpersonality (and personality itself), correlating with the journalistic work of the journalist-author, and a pole of institutionality, correlating with various aspects of media activity” Here it is necessary to note that “both poles are not separated, they intersect and interact intensively” [2, 44-45 p].

The intentional-situational conditionality of the discursive space of a newspaper text is a priority object of study in such integrative disciplines as pragmatististics, linguoculturology, discursive linguistics, the theory of speech influence, and sociolinguistics. At the same time, the focus is on the determination of the communicative effectiveness of media texts by their elocutionary organization, or in a non-terminological definition, “the manner of presentation of the material”. If we follow the principles of scientific (linguistic) presentation, then it should be noted that the elocutionary specificity of the texts that make up the modern mass media continuum is predetermined by a variety of communicative attitudes, the generalizing property of which is an appeal to the mass addressee in order to exert a maximum, pragmatically specified informing influence on him.

Pragmatic parameters of newspaper discourse as a significant component mass media sphere include goals (“for what”) and circumstances (“how”) of text creation, forming mechanisms for implementing strategic communication task. In this regard, the following problems caused by the functional dualism of media texts acquire particular importance: form of presentation of socially significant information, direct and indirect methods of speech influence; discursively determined trends in using an informative or influencing principle of organization text, the consequence of which is the alternation of “informemes” and “expressemes” in the speech structure of newspaper publications.

The main function of language is communication, but language is also capable of implementing a pragmatic function, that is, acting as an instrument of speech influence aimed at management of communication processes and promoting the formation of constructive value motivations, orientations and meanings. The pragmatic function of language is implemented most clearly and effectively in the media, which, according to most scientists, due to their ability to manage political and socio-economic processes, have become an instrument of social power with various capabilities and influence. Mediatization is the process and result of global influence on the thinking of individuals through various media, the main purpose of which is the formation of a special media picture of the world [3, 121–137 pp].

Modern media have moved away from direct pressure on the opinion of the audience, therefore the ideological position and assessment of the addressee are not imposed, but are hidden instilled in the addressee, who, following the author of the message, perceives a given assessment at the emotional or intellectual levels [4, 62-64 pp]. The media by their nature are deeply dialogical, since they are intended primarily to excite the reaction and response of the addressee, therefore communication in the media involves the interrelation of four main components, without which it cannot be implemented: goal, plan, text, reaction. In order to exert a manipulative influence on the consciousness of the addressee, the addressee can appeal to reason (logos), morality (ethos) and pathos (feelings, emotions) [5, 102-103 pp].

Mass media discourse is a special syncretic functional-style formation that has a differentiated impact on the widest possible audience by informing and evaluating the information communicated [6, 191-192 pp]. This type of discourse has the ability to model the national language, which is most clearly manifested in newspaper discourse, which is a reflection of the state of language in modern society, and the newspaper text is characterized by subjectivity, structural and functional integrity and orientation on the perception and interpretation of information through the creation of information and social mediation in order to exert a regulatory influence on public opinion and the formation of an individual’s ideas about reality through careful selection of information and the creation of various concepts, images, stereotypes and attitudes, communicated in explicit or hidden form [7, 123-124 pp]. The main specific features of newspaper discourse are territorial unlimitedness, mass character, emotionality and expressiveness, regularity, evaluativeness, relevance, informativeness and variety of topics, persuasiveness.

Mass media discourse, including newspaper discourse, regardless of the type of print publication (pro-government, independent, opposition), to one degree or another contains provocative and manipulative components and is aimed at forming or changing the addressee’s picture of the world, introducing this or that knowledge into his consciousness. Therefore, within the framework of the communicative-pragmatic direction, special attention is paid to the study of methods of speech behavior that are most effective in terms of the speaker’s strategy, as well as the choice of an adequate method of verbal influence on the addressee in a specific communicative situation.

According to A. A. Leontyev, there are three main ways to exert speech influence in the media:

1. informing by entering addressee concerns in the field new knowledge in order to change his attitude to reality;
2. informing through changing the recipient's concern field without introducing new elements into it, pushing recipients to reinterpret their existing knowledge;
3. Persuasion of addressees without communicating new information about the elements of the concern field, aimed at reprogramming the addressee's existing knowledge [8, 68 p].

Thus, in the process of speech influence, ontologization of knowledge occurs, in which, with the help of certain linguistic means, new knowledge is introduced into the addressee's world model and/or existing knowledge is changed, and the distinctive feature of speech influence is its hidden nature, that is, the addressee is not aware of the manipulation, but perceives it as part of objective information. In order to most effectively implement his intentions, the addresser uses various communicative strategies, tactics and speech techniques, which represent a complex system of planning a speech act for the successful carrying out of a communicative goal. Communication strategies are nationally and culturally determined models of speech behavior in a certain situation; therefore, each culture is characterized by its own set of methods, and techniques. Today, a large number of classifications of communication strategies and techniques have been developed, but the most common in mass media discourse are the presentation (self-presentation), the manipulation and the convention strategies. As part of a particular strategy, the addresser often appeals to the background knowledge of native speakers in order to create new associative connections based on existing ones, which actualize existing stereotypes, ideological, social and cultural values and norms in the addressee's mind, and indicate similarities in circumstances with those that took place in history of a particular society through the use of phraseological units, proverbs, sayings, aphorisms, etc. Thus, in Uzbek-language printed publications, the authors of newspaper texts often resort to mentioning historical events and well-known facts, hinting at the similarity of circumstances with those that took place in its history, and turn to scientific and religious images reflected in the culture of the Uzbek people: "*Yevropaga saboq bergan o'zbek allomalari: Turonzaminlik allomalarning turli fan sohalarida erishgan yutuklari Movorounnahrni, aniqrog'i, bu yerlik olimlarni butun jahonga mashhur qildi. Ular tomonidan qilingan kashfiyotlar esa hozirga qadar insoniyatni hayratlantirib kelayotir*" [X.S.2023.№ 125].

In American newspaper discourse, the main emphasis is on stereotyping when creating an image or representation of certain events, phenomena and individuals: "*AI? New jobs? California's local news deal with Google leaves lots of unanswered questions*" [LAT. 2024. September 20].

In Uzbek and American newspaper discourse, such stylistic devices as hyperbole, allegory, irony, allusion, metaphor, metonymy, oxymoron and others are widespread, which are used to enhance or weaken the impact of the statement on the addressee, to highlight or hide certain characteristics of the described phenomenon or object. In Uzbek and American newspapers, the most common methods of enhancing meaning are the repeated use of lexical units with a certain connotation and likening to an image that evokes certain positive or negative associations, and weakening the impact on the addressee, presenting information in the right way or hiding details occurs through the use of vocabulary with a wide and/or abstract meaning, borrowed vocabulary and mixing of genres. In addition, in Uzbek-language and English-language newspaper texts one can often find references to the words of an authoritative person and the inclusion of digital information in the text, carefully selected and interpreted in such a way that the addressee does not have doubts about the veracity of the addressee's words.

The category of evaluation, aimed at forming a primary attitude towards certain facts and phenomena, has the greatest speech-impacting potential in mass media discourse. There are various types of assessments (good - bad, positive - negative, legal - illegal, friend - enemy), but they all

contain not only approval or condemnation, but also elements of rational knowledge, therefore they can replace logical argumentation in the text, and often acquire nature of the arguments. When assessing a particular object, a linguistic personality always relies on ideal ideas about this object, which can be recognized as positively valuable, negatively valuable or value-neutral.

There are many different classifications of values, but one of the most complete and systematic is the classification developed by Yu. G. Veshninsky, who divides them into state-political, military-power, civil-legal values; historical values; communal values; natural values; scientific-cognitive values; personal values; religious and confessional values; social stratification values; artistic and aesthetic values; values of urban local-territorial communities; economic values; ethical values; ethnic values [9, 152 p]. While creating a newspaper text, addressees always appeal to generally accepted values rooted in a particular society. So, the most recognized values of the Uzbek people traditionally ethical and historical values are considered, for example, patriotism, justice, friendship, freedom, spirituality, generosity, mercy and etc., while in American society the first place comes civil and material values such as democracy, independence, law, equality, wealth, welfare and others.

The category of evaluation can be introduced in a media text both explicitly through a statement, reasoning, assumption, imperative, and implicitly through the use of invective means, tropes and figures of speech, imposing presuppositions and labeling, euphemization and dysphemization, the use of semantic gaps that the addressee is forced to unconsciously fill with judgments imposed on him. Thus, what comes first in modern media is not the informational, but the pragmatic function, which consists in interpreting information through the prism of a certain system of cultural values and political guidelines.

Newspaper discourse is an institutional-personal variety of discourse, functioning in the language of newspaper texts in a certain cultural and historical situation and having its own orientation, a certain set of linguistic means and participants. Newspaper texts always contain additional evaluative meanings aimed at exerting a manipulative influence on the consciousness of the addressee through the use of various linguistic means, techniques, as well as communicative strategies and tactics, thereby forming the necessary attitude towards the reported phenomenon. The most common speech techniques in English and Uzbek language newspaper discourse are hyperbole, allegory, irony, allusion, metaphor, metonymy, oxymoron and others, used by the addresser for the purpose of selecting and interpreting the necessary information, as well as enhancing the speech impact on the addressee.

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